

TELEMEDICINE

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Abstract: *Caring for health and well-being is very important for a person, which is clearly seen today. The medicine is the key to providing specialized advice to this patient. Individual attention is important in diagnosis because the same symptom may manifest differently in each person. The traditional experience of going to a specialist's office during a meeting is evolving with technology.*

In this way, many people now work from home or visit online art galleries, as well as have the opportunity to consult a medical question through a telemedicine service. Consultation of these features can be done remotely. However, the key to this medical care is nearby. Thus, both specialists and patients positively evaluate this experience.

Advantages of telemedicine

The patient appreciates the benefits that telemedicine offers. First, it provides maximum access. Technology and the Internet connection make this access possible from anywhere. On the other hand, you do not have to travel to be at the time specified in the consultation. The patient can live that moment from his home, a quiet and peaceful place for him.

Telemedicine has its place and place in today's society, but its task is not to replace the essence of the traditional approach. However, it is a good addition that has a positive effect on the most important thing: personal care.

There are significant changes in society that have taken place as a direct result of the pandemic. Companies, stores and businesses have undergone a digital transformation process. Digitization has also accelerated in previously delayed cases due to the priority of other corporate goals. Well, in another context, digitalization is also part of the healthcare industry. This is why some people have recently discovered the benefits of telemedicine for the first time.

Counseling is done through secure locations in a digital context. Videoconferencing is one of the most common formats for establishing direct communication between a professional and a patient. But this assistance can also be developed through courier services. Health information is part of a patient's medical history, which is confidential information. Therefore, telemedicine provides maximum security in accordance with the Data Protection Act.

Disadvantages of telemedicine

While the experience with this form of advice is very positive for many people, there are also obstacles to overcome them. One of them is insecurity created by an unknown truth. Not all patients and professionals know how to use this technology. Telemedicine is not adapted to any type of situation, situation or situation. There are evaluations that cannot be made through this route. This innovation is also weak under the influence of digital division.

Professionals in all fields need to add regular training to their careers to continue adding new skills and abilities. A clear example of telemedicine is training that accompanies healthcare professionals. This training only involves the development of technological skills. There is an ingredient that should never be lacking in personal attention: emotional intelligence. Compassion, listening, and politeness are critical to making each patient feel unique and unique in a traditional consultation or remote conversation.

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